

Program report Uganda

APRIL 2018

HUAWEI TECHNOLOGY COMPANY

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Declaration

I, Nanyonga Berinda, declare that this program report is of my own original piece of work. It is based on my personal experience while in China for the training.

Signed.....

Nanyonga Berinda

Acknowledgement

Saying, “Thank you,” can be difficult to do yet gratitude is important depending on the magnitude of the favor or the depth of appreciation involved. Simply put, I could not have done this work without the lots of help I received cheerfully from different souls.

My first vote of sincere thanks goes to God Almighty whose grace and love were sufficient enough for me throughout this period of the program. With the same spirit, I would like to extend my gratitude to the following people for their unconditional support in their various capacities;

Dr.Swaib Kyanda, Head of Networks Department, Makerere University and my final year project supervisor. He highly recommended me for the program and put me in contact with Professor Hugh Cameroon who gave us valuable instructions during the competition.

Lina Cao who took time off her busy schedule and dedicated it to guiding me so that I could maximally benefit from the program.

The entire panel during interviews especially Madam Barbara Nalubega who skillfully judged well and gave me a chance to be among the best ten lucky winners.

The Huawei guides; Aking and Nancy Wang. They were an epitome of strength and a great pillar of support. They were as loving as a mother and equally caring like a friend yet always approachable. You made the trip worth memorable.

My Chinese teachers; Xing Xiaoyan, Guo Rui, Shi Feiyu and Lee Shijie for accepting all us with all the weaknesses and working upon us to overcome them. They gave me extensive guidance regarding many practical issues.

Finally, I would especially like to thank my dearest mother for her enthusiastic encouragements during this period.

Throughout the program, I have learnt many things and the benefits are far beyond what I could have learnt in a normal project and therefore would like to thank Makerere University, Ministry of ICT, Ministry of Education and Sports, Uganda and Huawei Company for introducing me to this great opportunity in which I have developed myself both academically, professionally and socially, and whoever did their best in my stay in China, God richly bless you.

Dedication

This training report is dedicated to my precious family in appreciation for the financial and emotional support it has given me to see me through my studies up to this point. It is my promise that I will never let you down.

I would also like to dedicate it to my fellow software engineers, and to remind them that the development of our motherland, Uganda, depends on the technology we are to build and use in the future, plus the hard work we are ready and willing to offer.

Abstract

During the month of April 2018, I had the opportunity to participate in Huawei's Seeds for the Future program in Beijing and Shenzhen, China. The purpose of this program was to explore the young ICT talents by having a hands-on technology and cultural training for two weeks.

In the first week, we went to Beijing, the capital city of China where we were exposed to Chinese culture through visiting Chinese historical sites such as The Great Wall. We also attended classes to study the Chinese language. We were later examined on what we had studied and then travelled to Huawei headquarters in Shenzhen. This was mainly because of the hands-on technology training in which we were exposed to the key emerging technologies and their benefits to our daily life.

During this whole program, I got to know the other side of China. China is a world of its own and full of amazing and mind-blowing things. This study trip was indeed a road to Damascus.

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Full form
ICT	Information Communication Technology
IS	Information Systems
BLCU	Beijing Language and Cultural University
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
IoT	Internet of Things
ROADS	Real-time On-demand All-online DIY(Do It Yourself) Social
Iaas	Infrastructure as a service
Paas	Platform as a service
Saas	Software as a service

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CHAPTER 1: OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRAM.

This report contains my experience as a Ugandan student from Makerere University in the Huawei Technology Competitions under their Seeds for the Future Program 2018, in China from 6th April to 22nd April 2018.

1.1. Description of Huawei Company.

Huawei is a leading global Information and Communications Technology (ICT) solutions provider. Driven by a commitment to sound operations, ongoing innovation, and open collaboration, they have established a competitive ICT portfolio of end to end solutions in telecom and enterprise networks, devices, and cloud technology and services. Their ICT solutions, products, and services are used in more than 170 countries and regions, serving over one third of the world's population. With 180,000 employees and through different programs, Huawei is enabling the future information society and building a better-connected world.

1.2. Seeds for the Future Program.

The future program is Huawei's global CSR flagship program that was initiated in 2008. It is their most heavily invested CSR activity, and they continue to invest in the program over the long term.

The objectives for this program are;

2. To develop local ICT talent.
3. To improve and encourage regional building and participation in the digital community.
4. To enhance knowledge transfer.
5. To promote a greater understanding of and interest in the telecommunications sector.

In addition, the program has been implemented in 96 countries and international organizations worldwide, benefiting over 30,000 students from 280 universities, among them, more than 2,700 University students have taken a study trip to the Huawei Headquarters.

1.3. The Program in Uganda.

The Seeds for the Future Program started in Uganda in 2016 and was launched by His Excellency Yoweri Kaguta Museveni, The President of Uganda. This year, 2018, the ten students were flagged off by the First Lady Honorable Janet Museveni on 29th March at The State House.

Figure 1: A picture taken during the flag off ceremony by The First Lady at The State House.

Through this program, Huawei has been selecting top University students from ICT related disciplines who compete for the opportunity to travel to China for an intensive two-week tour of study in Beijing and Shenzhen. Huawei covers all travel and accommodation expenses for the ten winning students from the competition.

1.4. The competition.

Lecturers in different Universities recommended different students who had demonstrated high learning capacity and had strong potential to serve Uganda in their chosen field of study. Each candidate wrote a proposal in less than 500 words describing a current challenge to Uganda's economic development in a chosen thematic area and clearly suggested a solution by using ICT and networks in the implementation. I therefore based my proposal on the increasing car insecurity cases in urban parking lots. I suggested the development of a Biometric Based Car to Driver Matching Security System that would match the car number plate to its driver's biometric at entrance and compares the two at exit. In cases, of a mismatch, an alarm would be made in addition to the notification sent to the driver whose first details were captured. My proposal was among the best 20 that were chosen, and I had to face the panel, comprising of 7 judges to defend it which I wisely did and was chosen among the best ten to represent Uganda in China.

CHAPTER 2: PROGRAM ACTIVITIES IN CHINA

This section describes the different activities that I participated in during my study trip in Beijing and Shenzhen, China. Most of these activities are based on the scheduled timetable that we had from the time we set our first feet in China to the time we left Hong Kong International Airport back to Uganda.

2.1. Beijing Activities

2.1.1. Introduction.

Beijing is made up of Chinese characters , “bei” to mean north and “jing” means capital therefore Beijing means northern capital, referring to the city’s location in the north of China.[1] The activities here concerned learning Chinese and experiencing Chinese culture and these included the following;

2.1.2. The City Tour.

We reached Beijing on Saturday evening and could not wait for the city tour on Sunday. I was so amused by the Bicycle Sharing System where by everyone has equal rights over that bicycle. Different people ride the bicycles and leave them on the roads for others to use if one’s phone can scan the QR code on the bicycle. I was also amused by the electronic buses that charge using the wires hanging up in the air as if electricity wires connected by poles. There was more to explore in Beijing;

2.1.2.1. The Great Wall.

The Great Wall of China is one of the greatest wonders of the world and going to China means climbing it. We arrived in China on Saturday and none of us could wait for that Sunday morning. The weather seemed so cold, we had a heavy breakfast and got into the bus for the great journey in the north. Our tourist guide went on giving us more details about the wall which was first completed in the Qin Dynasty (221-206 BC) and was last rebuilt as a defense in the Ming Dynasty (1368-1644). It protected China’s north from invasion. [2]

We climbed the wall so high till when I could not feel my legs anymore. This was my greatest challenge and most interesting experience in China. I met very many people from different countries and as usual I took enough pictures before heading to the food market.

2.1.2.2. The Wang Fujing Food Street.

Generally, the Chinese have different eating habits from Africans, but food remains food despite the different styles of preparing it. I had the greatest pleasure of visiting the Wang fujing food street, a famous walking street in Beijing known for its various selection of things to eat. Even though most meat make rare appearance on menus, the Chinese still make everything available because they view the whole animal as food. I saw lots of sea food at the market and we all looked surprised at the different seasoned kinds of street food such as deep-fried lizards, crickets, scorpions and crunchy star fish on sticks.

Figure 2: A picture of some foods in the Wang Fujing food street market

2.1.2.3. The Forbidden City.

The imperial palace of the Ming and Qing Dynasties is a world heritage site because of its development of Chinese architecture and culture. It was a great feeling touring the site which covers an area of 720,000 square meters with 890 buildings and a peripheral wall. [3] I found it so amusing that everything in the city was constructed for a reason starting with the nails on all doors to the animal statues. The palace officially contains a total of 9999.5 rooms since the emperor could have only this maximum number of rooms on earth and only the palace in the sky as the paradise in heaven was called, could have 10,000 rooms. Everything about this beautiful place was nice to people like me who are in to adventure.

2.1.3. Studying at the School of Continuing Education of BLCU.

We had had a long fun week-end but the new week of classes had started. Studying at BLCU is part of the program to enable international students learn the basics of the Chinese language and experience their culture. The teaching system emphasizes time management in both students and teachers. The program was well organized for example campus cards at the canteen were offered on the first day and were returned to the reception upon leaving. Class schedule and handouts were also distributed upon arrival in class. The handouts were designed for Chinese lessons, lectures on Chinese culture, Chinese songs and other supporting materials.

2.1.3.1. Cultural lessons

These lessons were for calligraphy by Guo Rui Lao shi and Shi Feiyu Lao shi for Chinese painting which both started at 2:00pm up to 3:50pm on different days.

2.1.3.1.1. Calligraphy.

The Chinese calligraphy is a unique visual art which reflects their characters and has developed for over 3000 years of evolution. Guo Rui taught us the four study treasures; the ink brush (bǐ), Chinese ink (mò), paper (zhǐ) and the ink stone (yàn). He also taught us how to hold and maintain the tools.

Figure 3: Different pictures of my painting and calligraphy work with my respective teachers.

2.1.3.1.2 Chinese painting.

The painting which paint by brush dipped on water, ink and color through silk paper. The painting is classified into three types depending on the technique used namely; freestyle, traditional Chinese realistic painting and the combination of these two techniques. We mainly concentrated on free style because it was much easier than others.

2.1.3.2. Chinese lessons

These were lessons to study comprehensive Chinese from 9:00am up to 11:50am. Our teacher was called Xing Xiaoyan, Lao shi to mean teacher in Chinese. She taught us self-introductions and daily expressions using the famous Chinese phonetics (initials, finals and tones). Truth be told, Chinese seems hard to be learnt but it is the best language to study. The most important thing to know are the tones because every tone gives a different meaning.

In addition to class activities, the teachers also taught us some famous Chinese songs during the ten minute break. The songs included “Tian mi mi” to mean Honey Sweet by Teresa Teng and “Péngyǒu” to mean friend. Also, every student was required to write a test on the last day before credited a certificate during the closing ceremony.

2.1.4. The Closing Ceremony

Every student looked forward for this day. Back to me, I didn't wish this day to come because I had made friends in the University and knew that this would keep my heart weary. After all the sleepless nights of practicing Chinese, we were encouraged to be actively involved in this ceremony which included; role plays in Chinese and singing Chinese songs. The ceremony was a successful one with our Ugandan mime of Born in Africa song by the legend Philly Lutaya.

2.1.5. The Hot Pot Dinner

Of all the things we did in Beijing, this was the most unforgettable moment of my dear friends. It was the right time to show how well one could cook for him or herself. Being our last night in Beijing, we could not leave without visiting Xiebuxiabu restaurant for best hot pot dinner. None of us had an idea what hot pot meant. For minutes, from the moment we walked in the door, the waitresses could sense that we were out of element. We kept on looking at each other and wondered what to do. Fortunately, Lina and A king took control of the whole process which involved split

broth pots, pans of searing, gas stoves and small plates. They took us to the fresh display case of sliced meat, chopped vegetables and dumplings. To ensure that the hot pot experience was perfect, the two guides regularly monitored our tables, from afar and up close. We got new ingredients from the waitresses that we felt were essential for cooking or creating new dipping sauces.

Figure 4: A picture taken during the Hot Pot dinner.

The Chinese hot pot concept is simple, simmering meat, vegetables and noodles in spicy or pain broth fondue in the center of the center. At the end of this dinner, I realized that there was more to discover about China though time was not on our side.

We left Beijing on Thursday 13th of April and flew straight to the mighty Shenzhen city. I could not wait to arrive in the City of the Future.

2.2. Shenzhen Activities.

2.2.1. Introduction

When it comes to enjoying technology, one must talk about the Shenzhen city in southern China. Shenzhen, a city of around 11 million people, is now merely the world's largest continuously urbanized area. [4] A generation ago, it was just a quiet fishing village of some 30,000 across the border from Hong Kong. Then, in 1979, the Chinese government turned it into an experiment to grow capitalism in a test tube, designating it as the country's first special economic zone. [5] Every activity in this city was mind blowing.

2.2.2. City Tour in Shenzhen

During our meetings in Uganda, Professor Hugh distributed some books that we would read before setting off for the trip. I only looked out for pictures and could not wait for the beautiful sight in Shenzhen. The whole journey on the bus, I was just looking out to the amazing skyscrapers. I was privileged enough to see The Ping An Finance Centre, the fourth tallest building in the world.[6] There were more to explore in Shenzhen;

2.2.2.1. The China Cultural Folk Village

This was the most beautiful place I had visited in my whole life. The place is a comprehensive miniature park reflecting the history, culture, art, ancient architecture, and customs and habits of various nationalities in China. It is one of the world largest scenery parks in the number of scenarios reproduced of Shenzhen Metro), or 30 minutes by bus.

Over 100 major tourist attractions have been miniaturized and laid out according to the map of China. Most attractions have been reduced on a scale of 1:15. It is divided into Scenic Spot Area and Comprehensive Service Area. The entire park covers 30 hectares. [7]

We took a train around the park which made it possible to visit The Great Wall, The Forbidden City, Potala Palace and The Terracotta Army. We also attended depicting various events in Chinese History and Chinese cultural which were performed with lots of skills.

2.2.2.2. The Shenzhen Museum

The construction of different statues to illustrate real people was really something new to our sights. We were taught the history of Shenzhen from a local fishing ground to an economic urban city it is today.

Figure 5: A picture of statues illustrating how people worked hard to develop the current Shenzhen city.

It was from this place that I realized that the city currently has younger female hardworking people than the males which strengthened my hope of bringing change to my country as a young educated woman.

2.2.2.3. Shopping at the mega markets.

Everyone was excited about shopping because we were to be exposed to the latest gadgets in China. We particularly went to Hua Giang Bei electronics, the world's greatest electronics market, [6], Luohu Commercial City, an enclosed shopping mall close to Hong Kong Shenzhen port and the Dongmen Market, Shenzhen's original shopping mall. China's markets are much bigger than what I had seen in Uganda. The whole street was full of one product and therefore we could not look at everything. There were so many copy products at higher prices and negotiation was hard due to language difficulties.

2.2.3. Huawei Exhibition Hall visit

In the exhibition hall, Huawei showcases what kind of services might be possible applying especially next generation mobile technology and 5G. What amused me was that Huawei has developed a smart camera “a smart camera that detects the loudest noise made by a person and displays that actual persons face on the screen in less than seconds”. One application scenario according to me, might be attention solutions in conferences where the speakers face is the only thing displayed to listeners and viewers. We also got a chance to tour the Huawei base. I liked the natural beauty that the company has maintained at the base. The small water bodies brought out the whole beauty of the area plus the beautiful flowers.

Figure 6: A picture at the lake found at the Huawei Base.

2.2.4. The Huawei orientation

This was the overview of Huawei Company as a successful business at Huawei headquarters and to take us through of what was required of us during our stay in the new city. As an organized company, we were happily welcomed at the training center by Nancy and Khloe. We went to the classroom in which every student was given a bag containing lesson material and pocket translators for communication. Khloe took us through the dress code expected within the Huawei premises and told us more about our stay in Shenzhen. We also had a chance to interact with Carol, a software engineer at Huawei Company, who explained to us the company core values, vision, history, the driving factors and its future. She gave me more ideas on my career path decisions.

2.2.5. Birthday Celebrations

One of the greatest experience that I can't forget about the program is that it made my 2018 birthday very memorable. I had a chance to enjoy my day with special friends that had become family in a week. The Myanmar group was so nice to me that it made me feel so happy. Thanks to Nancy who made me a sweet party and to the Amber Plaza workers for the sweet cake. The day was really made special that I can never forget it. I was so lucky that even Nancy had her birthday during our stay in Shenzhen and it also called for celebrations.

Figure 7: A picture during the birthday celebrations before cutting the cake.

2.2.6. Classes at the Huawei Training Center

Classes at the training center were the most serious lessons I had had in my entire life. We were taught by a knowledgeable trainer called Lee Shijie who was lineate to every student and encouraged individual participation which helped us to focus in class. He mainly taught us; Telecommunication Network, The Emerging Key Technologies of ICT, 4G Base Station Data Configuration and base station practical in the laboratory.

2.2.6.1. Telecommunication Network

During these classes, we were mainly focused on services in the mobile network such as mobile voice service and data service, and those in fixed networks such as fixed home service, home broadband service, IPTV and IP Phone. We also looked at the different generations of the Mobile Communication System including the mobile network evolution from 1G to 4.5G.

2.2.6.2. The Emerging Key Technologies of ICT

Due to the introduction of new technologies, we were lucky enough to get exposed to the current trends which are cloud computing, IoT and 5G technologies. These technologies are based on the new norm of experience (ROADS) which aims at ubiquitous, high speed reliable and real time intelligent connectivity. Cloud computing in its different models helps in various ways for example IaaS model allows organizations to outsource computing equipment and resources, PaaS model enables software developers to streamline the development process by shifting specific aspects of systems management to service provider and lastly SaaS model delivers on-demand applications that are hosted and managed by the service provider. A very good example of cloud computing was the use of Google Docs, offered Google.

On the other hand, 5G technology will connect all things in our daily life and all industries will be transformed through digitalization for example self-driving cars, mission critical applications and work and play in the cloud. IoT solutions include smart home, E-Health, connected cars and safe city.

All these technologies will make wonders especially in Uganda where agriculture is the back bone of our economy. Digitalizing this industry will bring far much development than it is now.

2.2.6.3. 4G Base Station Data Configuration.

This was practical, and everyone was required to wear the laboratory coat for safety. We prepared for the experiment and carried it out individually using the test Huawei phones with the help of Lee and another laboratory attendant.

The next day, we had to write an exam basing on what we had started in classes which lasted for an hour before we went for the graduation ceremony.

2.2.7. Huawei Graduation Ceremony

Unlike the Beijing closing ceremony, this one was very special to everyone because there were two countries to perform, Uganda and Myanmar. Time was the greatest aspect for that day. There were more cameras around and the journalists were more than I accepted. We performed Judith Babirye's song entitled "Ndi munauganda" to mean I am a Ugandan. We also performed a joined song with the Myanmar group to show how close Huawei had put us close.

Figure 8: A picture of the joint performance by both groups at the closing ceremony.

We received our certificates and then a heavy lunch and endless pictures. This was such a sorrowful moment for everyone especially for the friends we had made in Huawei. All this was consoled with the endless dance we had altogether before we headed for Hon Kong that evening.

CHAPTER 3: DISCUSSION OF THE EXPERIENCE

This program was where my mind was opened to the real world because it revealed to me the hidden side of China.

3.1. New knowledge and skills gained.

I learned Chinese culture and language which I can use to communicate. I also learnt how to use chopsticks.

I adopted the Chinese time management skill and how to utilize the valuable resources.

I learned the key emerging technologies influencing the strategy of Huawei which include 5G, IoT and cloud computing and their benefits.

I explored a lot about the Huawei Company; its basic tips of being a successful global company, the driving factors and the core values. These are the same tips to use to develop Uganda.

I strengthened my presentation skills through class presentations and interviews by different journalists.

I clearly understood the difference between IT and ICT.

I learned how to responsibly take care of myself while in a foreign country especially at the airport.

I learned how to configure a 3G Base Station since I practically participated in the laboratory.

I gained instructional technique skills to help develop and implement IT strategically.

I widened my knowledge of telecommunication and mobile networks.

3.2. Most interesting experiences.

The whole period of the program was amazing to me, but some moments were exceptional such as;

Visiting the historical places of China especially climbing the Great Wall of China with different people of different nationalities.

Studying Chinese characters and tones at BLCU and being interviewed by journalists.

Special treatment at the luxurious hotels with a swimming pool. We were treated as VIPs. The swimming pool was free of charge and some students went for gym.

Exploring the different fierce Chinese dishes in different restaurants.

Having hands on experience to work with equipment and technology that is not available in Uganda for example 5G and the cameras that sensed noise at the Huawei exhibition hall.

Going for shopping.

Enjoying Wi-Fi from the time we started the journey till when we came back to Uganda.

My birthday celebration in an Indian Chinese restaurant. This was my best of all birthdays in my entire life. The celebrations were forever memorable.

3.3. Relatedness of University taught programs to the program.

I was so privileged to have done this training in China because there was a lot to be learnt since I nearly found no comparison between the program and what we studied back in Makerere University. The technologies in China were too advanced and the Chinese and cultural lessons were far different from what we studied in Software Engineering programs. However, exploring the telecommunication network required some knowledge from Data communication, a program I had studied while at the University. During this program, I was taught the different examples of tele-services, their advantages and disadvantages most of which are best described under the program activities. The program also emphasized team work which is a quality of all projects carried out at the University.

In addition to the above, I was able to write all the necessary essays required in the program using the skills that I learnt during the Research methodology program while at the University.

3.4. Challenges Faced

Despite the good times I had in China, I cannot deny the fact that there were sometimes when I found life complicated for me during the program and these included the following;

I found it hard to adopt the Chinese styles of preparing food and enjoy my meals. Some foods were hard to eat at the thought of biting them especially the sea food.

The weather was a bit non friendly. We travelled at the time when Beijing was very cold and being in class was even worse. Coming from an equatorial climatic country like Uganda, there was no way I could enjoy my stay in China when the weather is so cold.

Language difficulties during shopping and exchanging currencies at the banks.

In addition, there was a time when I missed home since it was so expensive to make international calls and yet we had local lines. On the other hand, all the common social media platforms were blocked hence making communication back home more complicated.

Lastly, the time for the program was too short for me to understand most things in classes taught at a fast pace. The teachers were so eager to catch up with time and so I had to adjust to their speed to pick something.

3.5. Benefits derived from the program

I believe this program was a solid investment in my future because it paid in many various ways. This section outlines all the benefits that were derived from the Seeds for the Future program.

3.5.1. To student.

I strengthened my academic program through a better use of my elective credits. This added more credit to my transcript hence making me out stand from job competition.

I converted my academic knowledge into industry skills. Configuring the 3g base station gave me hope to have confidence in my own abilities.

I made industry contacts which is vital in helping me find and secure a job after school. Life is based on ‘it’s not about what you known; it’s about who you know’. I interacted closely with most people hence developing professional working relationships with Huawei Company and the University at large.

I have gained unforgettable life experience and developed self-confidence from the TV interviews in China in addition to the exposure of real world problems and solutions.

3.5.2. To Huawei Company

The program created the opportunity to recruit future employees and to evaluate prospective employees virtually risk free.

The program strengthened the bond with the University and Uganda at large.

The program enables the company to achieve its core value of customer centric hence good brand management

3.5.3. To Makerere University.

The program validated university's curriculum in an international working environment.

The program may accelerate corporate fund-raising efforts.

The program connected the ICT faculty to current international trends within their professional field.

The program enabled the University to identify its main competitors in ICT programs. This was mainly during the competitions before the study tour.

The program developed more competitive and hardworking graduates.

3.6. Career motivation

After the training, I got a career path that suited me since I prefer a varied career to moving into management roles. This motivated me to first work for an organization to maintain my interest and keep learning. This career progression has taken me out of the ICT area altogether as I find other activities that incites my passion and narrow down to my list of potential careers.

In addition to the above, the program has motivated me to lay the building blocks for my future by setting a foundation for my career basing on my focus and identifying my talents and abilities. This will help me make a better career path decision.

CHAPTER 4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS.

This section emphasizes the important areas of the report and makes suggestions to strengthen the China program as global CSR at Huawei Company.

4.1. Conclusion

All in all, my program experience as a Ugandan student in China was more beneficial than what I expected, and I don't regret anything. I gained technological and cultural skill development, professional connections, and the opportunity to represent to be a good ambassador of my nation, Uganda. I enjoyed every chance that I got despite the challenges that hindered perfection. With the following recommendations, some challenges can be managed.

4.2. Recommendations

According to my program experience, I described the challenges I faced as an individual and the students team at large. This section therefore includes suggestions for improvement in the program and advise other seeds for the future program.

The program should be scheduled in accordance to University timetables so that students travel after exams. It brings tension if students must travel to China and return for exams.

Huawei should follow up the student proposals hence making reality out of them. This will help students apply the new knowledge and skills to contribute to the economy Uganda.

Huawei should also give priority to the program beneficiaries in all the possible opportunities so that connections are maintained. It is much easier to work with people you are already used to.

Students are advised to learn some Chinese before participating in any Chinese program. This makes work much easier for both sides.

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Appendices

This section includes the additional material providing further information to the report

Appendix 1: Pictures during the city tours.

Figure 9: Pictures at during the city tours in both cities.

Appendix 2: Pictures during meals time.

Appendix 3: Pictures in the laboratory

Appendix 4: Pictures of Huawei base tour

Appendix 5: The closing ceremony pictures.

Appendix 7: The BLCU essay

This is the essay that we were required to hand in before leaving Beijing commenting on the teachers at BLCU.

CLASS EXPERIENCE IN BEIJING LANGUAGE AND CULTURAL UNIVERSITY

When Huawei Company sent me the schedule of my Beijing study tour, as any other University student, I was hurt that classes were part of the tour. Despite the excitement of being in a foreign country for the first time, deep down in my heart I was sad because I expected the worst from China classes knowing that Chinese doesn't speak English. I kept on wondering how hard it would be for me to pass the exams that were scheduled on my last day in Beijing. Little did I know that I was about to experience some of the best moments in a life.

It was a very cold morning on 9th of April 2018 that marked the beginning of the way I thought about Chinese classes, particularly in Beijing Language and Cultural University (BLCU) which is best known for teaching and promoting Chinese ancient culture. I have only had three days of class, but I still feel that the experience I have is as though for years. During my study tour, I have had three wonderful teachers, who have helped me explore the skills I had ignored while in my previous schools. Xing Xiaoyan and Guo Rui, both women who have taught me comprehensive Chinese and calligraphy respectively while Shi Feiyu was the only male who has taught me Chinese painting. All these were being taught to me in room 331, which was a small room and always clean compared to those in Uganda. I have spent more time with Xing Xiaoyan and she has totally changed my attitude I had towards female teachers in high schools. She has been so motherly to me though one with cool jokes, she always made sure that everyone learnt Chinese sounds. She has really done a great job in teaching me how to speak Chinese. In cases of questions, she has been eager to answer me even though some answers were missed because of the language difficulty. I can never regret the times I have spent in her classes because there has been no time I felt that she was boring because she even got time to teach us the Chinese songs in the 10-minute break. I failed to tell her age by her appearance but the way she conducted herself, was enough to let me know that she was a respectful woman blessed with a golden heart. She has always been in time for classes and a teacher who never delayed us after classes. On the other hand, the few hours I had with the other two teachers have also been a blessing to me. They were so kind and always willing to help me. I have learnt how to write my name in Chinese and do painting. These teachers taught with a passion and I believe that they all set good examples of how friendly and respectful a teacher and student relationship should be in universities. We used to have lunch for longer hours than in Uganda, but my good teachers would still feel strong in the afternoon classes.

All in all, I am going back to Uganda and because of this great relationship with my teachers, I pray to keep in touch with them. They are friends that I would not let go that easily. I am willing to keep in touch with all my friends from Beijing because they are the reason I felt home away from home. The world would be a better place if all teachers were like my Beijing teachers because we would be sure that children are being groomed in a perfect environment. I have really found Chinese culture so interesting and one that every person needs to know.

Special thanks go to Huawei Company for this greatest opportunity of studying the Chinese culture but above all for choosing the best teachers to take me through the classes.

Appendix 8: The Huawei essay

This is the same essay that we were required to write after the training at the Huawei University.

COUNTRY: UGANDA

NAME: NANYONGA BERINDA

SUGGESTIONS OF IMPROVING INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY IN UGANDA.

It is worldly known that “Experience is the greatest teacher” and indeed I have come to a total agreement with that saying. Special thanks go to Huawei Technologies Company, under its program “seeds for the future 2018”, for giving me a two-week cultural and technology training opportunity. This has been the greatest experience that I will live to share with the future generation. I have learnt and gained a lot of knowledge which I can now use to improve the Information Technology in my country, Uganda through the following suggestions;

First and foremost, all Ugandans must change their mind sets by starting to embrace change. Improving technology focuses on planning for the future and leaving behind the conservative and traditional way of thinking. This will pave way for strong minds to become creative and innovative hence improving Information Communication Technology in Uganda.

The government should invest more resources in the technology sector especially in the institutions that teach the technology skills for example equipment should be freely provided to young innovators who make embedded system projects or capital should be given to them to implement these projects. Embedded system projects are very expensive and therefore must be sponsored hence encouraging more successful innovations in Uganda. The main challenge facing innovators in Uganda is lack of sufficient funds and this greatly affects the improvement of Information Communication Technology because it makes projects unsuccessful.

The teaching style in Uganda should be greatly changed in a way that students should be given more chances to practice the theories in well-equipped laboratories. Technology is all about bringing innovative ideas into reality and this can only be done through practical. In most times, skills are gained from practical but not theories because the two describe something in a different way. During my training, I configured a 4G base station using steps from a book and this taught me a lot. It seemed harder while reading from the book but then it was a walk over in the laboratory. Knowing that action speaks louder than words, every student must have practical if technology is to be improved in Uganda.

Throughout the whole program, I have had amazing moments in places that describe China’s poetic and natural beauty such as the China splendid and cultural village and the Shenzhen exhibition museum. These are places that have used the digital knowledge to preserve the environment and ancient times of China. Uganda must learn that technology is not ignoring nature and culture. We can combine all using technology to eradicate computer illiteracy in Uganda because such places will also require digital knowledge.

I suggest that the government should strengthen its ties with the China government so as Ugandan students get more chances to have such programs and explore the real world of technology. The training has really promoted my team work skills because it was all about working together with people who are totally different but end up becoming a happy family.

I also suggest that Ugandans should be encouraged to develop the Ugandan spirit to improve technology in the country. People need to work so hard and be very determined for technology to be successful. The Chinese people work so hard and never accept defeat or failures. They always quench for more and more. This is the kind of the spirit we need to move our lives into the digital world.

In my conclusion, there are always many ways of killing a rat, but we take the easiest way. The development pace at which my country is moving is worrying but that doesn't mean that we should give up. It's all about moving forward and ignore the failures. Nothing is too hard to be accomplished if it was well started. We Ugandans need to stand up straight and explore the world for technology to improve. All it takes is for you to be innovative and creative, and this is what the future holds.

End of report